

IMPACT OF PART-TIME JOB ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND SATISFACTION: A CASE OF TEACHER EDUCATION PROGRAM AT INTERNATIONAL ISLAMIC UNIVERSITY ISLAMABAD

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ABSTRACT

Students' academic achievement and their satisfaction related to their studies are influenced by part-time employment. The study's objectives were: (a) to examine the effects of part-time jobs on students' academic achievement and satisfaction at the university level. (b) to identify factors that influence students to seek part-time jobs. (c) to study the effects of the number of hours of part-time jobs on students' academic achievement and satisfaction. The design of the study was qualitative research. All those students who were engaged with part-time jobs and were enrolled in some degree program at International Islamic University were the population of the study. The sample of the study was comprised of 14 students of B. Ed. A purposive sampling technique was used to select respondents. A structured interview was designed to collect data. Qualitative thematic analysis was done to analyze data. Results of the study show that part-time job affects students positively and negatively. Based on study results, it is recommended that teachers understand the engagement of working students so the stress of these students may be reduced to some extent.

KEYWORDS: Part-time job, academic achievement, Working students, basic needs, and financial responsibilities

1. INTRODUCTION

A part-time job is considered a modern type of job that students can continue during their studies to cope with the different needs of life (Tessema et al., 2014). A part-time job is a help for individuals who may not get a full-time job for some reason (Moro-Egido & Panades, 2010). Part-time jobs enable individuals to fulfill their needs for whom the salary package is too low to compensate for their basic needs. Further part-time job enables students to continue their studies without burdening their parents. Students who do part-time jobs can affect the company or organization with their latest knowledge of skills; employers can get an advantage from part-time students (Čemerková, Šebestová & Šperka, 2018). Students have practiced part-time jobs at different levels for a long time. Unfortunately, today's scenario and the decreasing economic condition of the country have brought students to part-time jobs so that their parents cannot burden them and can fulfill their own needs and demands of education on their own. There is no data found by which researchers can estimate the exact number of students who are doing part-time jobs (Sampelolo and Atmowardoyo, 2016). Several studies show that 50 to 60 % of university students are practicing part-time jobs while studying (Watts, 2002).

Many reasons can be considered for doing a part-time job for students. First, the annual expenditure on the education system and day-to-day living continuously increases. Some researchers suggest that a child's home's low economic condition is the fundamental reason for doing a part-time job (Tam Oi I & Morrison, 2005). This trend is becoming high day by day, and this scenario is affecting students' academic performance and achievement. Secondly, students gain hands-on experience in the work, and part-time work enables them to master different skills that students can use in their employment after graduation. These experiences cannot be gained through actual classroom situations, only during teaching and learning. This issue is addressed by many researchers worldwide (Curtis & Shani, 2002). Previous research addressed the issues of working hours and the relevance of the part-time job with the academic discipline so that the relationship between the part-time job and the student's academic achievements can be checked (Sampelolo &

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Atmowardoyo, 2016). There is a firm belief that students cannot get good grades while doing part-time jobs; thus, they lack in every activity of the classroom and the institution (Neill et al., 2004). The reason is that students cannot focus on their studies while doing work, and good results can be acquired only when they concentrate on their studies with full intention and devotion. Much research on university students has been conducted from this perspective in developed countries. In developing countries like Pakistan, there is a low level of research conducted in this area. Therefore, this study aims to analyze the effects of part-time jobs on students' academic achievement and performance at the university level.

1.1. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study will be to:

- Examine the effects of part-time jobs on students' academic achievement and satisfaction of the students.
- Find out factors that influence students to seek part-time jobs.
- Study the effects of the number of hours of part-time jobs on students' academic achievement and satisfaction.

1.2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions will be addressed:

- How do part-time jobs affect students' academic achievement and satisfaction?
- What are the factors that influence students to seek part-time jobs?
- How does the number of hours affect students' academic achievement and satisfaction?

1.3. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This research is helpful for researchers as well as students in understanding the extent to which part-time jobs affect academic achievement. It will help to find possible solutions to make part-time jobs effective for students' academic achievements. The study is beneficial for identifying the existing status of part-time jobs so that higher education students can understand their ability to face problems while doing part-time jobs. It will help future researchers in their research related to problems of part-time jobs.

1.4. DELIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This study was delimited to B. ed students of the Department of Education of International Islamic University Islamabad.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Part-time job is now considered a normal fact instead of an unusual phenomenon (Patton and Smith, 2009). Most organizations are now demanding and recruiting students for their work as students have the latest ground knowledge of the field and much more capability and enthusiasm to deal with the work. Some students join these organizations for the sake of their families, and some join to spare their time in an effective way to get expertise. Keeping in view the demands of the students, the institutional head and other staff is now accepting the students who are doing a part-time job (Yin & Lei, 2007)

2.1. PART-TIME JOB

Part-time employment is a type of job that consists of fewer hours than the hours of a full-time job (Tam Oi I & Morrison, 2005). Job is considered part-time when workers work 30 to 35 hours per week. Regarding working hours for part-time employment, countries tend to have different working hours and conditions (Muluk, 2017). In Australia, the hours required to do a part-time job are 32 per week. In Canada, a part-time job lasts 30 hours per week. In France, the duration of work per hour is 45 per month (Patton & Smith, 2010). In Spain, work is part-time if the hours of the job don't go beyond two-thirds of the workers in the full-time job. In the UK and Ireland, the time required for a part-time job is 30 hours per week. According to the Bureau of Labour Statistics, the time required for a part-time job is between 1 to 34 hours per week.

Regarding part-time jobs, workers do not have the power and other facilities compared to full-time jobs. In America, part-time workers are not given the benefits such as health assurance and educational facilities given to full-time workers. Considering the above definitions, the researcher can conclude that students who do part-time jobs are those who work during the semesters with 20 hours per week. Students try to work full-time after the semester or during the semester break. (Moro-Egido & Panades, 2010)

2.2. EMPLOYMENT WHILE STUDYING

The trend of doing part-time jobs is increasing day by day in every country of the world. Barron (2006) found 9 out of 10 students work part-time in Australian universities. Barron's findings align with the findings of Anyanwu (1998), who pointed out that almost all Australian students work part-time 30 hours per week to fulfill their personal and study needs. Watts and Pickering (2000) found that in the UK, working part-time is increasing rapidly, and it has become a common phenomenon. This phenomenon has powerful positive effects on students and their families. Students do part-time jobs to fulfill the necessities of their education. Moreover, they found that 8 out of 10 students worked part-time jobs.

View students' part-time jobs as based on the actual world of work, and their gained experience from part-time jobs enables them to be successful individuals in society. It also provides help in the development of their career. Part-time jobs enhance the students' learning in the actual classroom by giving them hands-on experience. The part-time job should be closely related to learned knowledge, whether it be through formal or informal ways (Robotham, 2012). According to the Dearing Report on Higher Education, higher education must enable students to be aware of the work by identifying various prospects and opportunities and guiding the students to reflect on those experiences (Sekiguchi, 2012). In Australia, Nelson's higher education reforms mainly focus on university funding and motivate individuals and universities to keep in view the economic and commercial outlook (Patton and Smith, 2009). Universities and work organizations should work together to develop the linkage between students' work experiences, their actual classroom situation and employability (Kwadzo, 2014).

2.3. DEMAND FOR STUDENTS

Workplaces and work organizations (Darmody and Smyth, 2008) demand students because students tend to do work on a reasonable and low level of payment. This helps employers get good quality work from students without paying many salaries. Secondly, students' demands in the workplace are high because students have fresh and latest knowledge of the situation; in this way, students can place the organization in good status and up to date. Thirdly, students believe in flexibility as they obey orders quickly. Employers can easily change their work hours to cope with the market demand, the type of work that needs more focus than other activities and other facilities (Čemerková et al., 2018). Furthermore, workplace managers or leaders can take advantage of the students by providing them with extra work they don't tend to do while entering the workplace or organization (Lin and Ching, 2014). Furthermore, students have qualities that actual employees of the organizations are lacking. In this way, employers can take advantage of the students and warmly welcome them to do part-time jobs in their organization (Callender, 2008). These qualities may be intelligence, creativity, management, presentation skills and good communication.

2.4. THE NECESSITY FOR PART-TIME EMPLOYMENT

Today, the cost of education is very high for students who come from middle-class families. These families fulfill their basic needs so hard that they cannot afford to educate their children at the university level (Hunt et al., 2004). Students from these families do part-time jobs to fulfill their education needs and necessities so their parents may not burden them. Secondly, part-time jobs allow students to get workplace experience that can be helpful in their future professional life (Metcalf, (2003). They learn the environment and workplace requirements and how to start their career. Moreover, a part-time job allows students to learn about the importance of teamwork, good communication and hands-on training. These skills can be applied in the actual profession by which they can maximize their performance in the workplace, and these skills are most important for those students who are studying technical and vocational courses. These students can directly align their learning skills in part-time jobs and their learned knowledge in a workplace environment. This practice helps students to enhance their knowledge and motivation (Body et al., 2014). No doubt, part-time jobs enable students to get experience in the workplace and make the students more competent than those who don't do part-time jobs. Moreover, by doing part-time jobs, students can be helpful to their families to lessen their financial burden, including their educational costs. Further, students can enhance and learn what different career opportunities are for them and which will suit them better (Dumont et al., 2009).

2.5. BALANCING EDUCATION AND PART-TIME WORK

It is difficult for students who do part-time jobs to maintain the educational processes and workplace requirements simultaneously. Because students cannot focus on their education correctly due to lack of time, they spend on part-time jobs (Tam Oi I & Morrison, 2005). Students tried their best to balance the institutional and workplace requirements. Some suffer from hypertension and stress as they cannot fully concentrate on both sides. This stress badly affects students' mental as well as physical health. In turn, students' condition leads to poor performance in their studies and the workplace (Barron, 2007). A part-time job does not always lead to bad performance. Students can perform best, get good marks, and perform well in the workplace if the working hours are manageable and the work is according to the student's interests. Therefore, students must choose suitable part-time jobs so that they can have a balance between educational processes and workplace demands and performance.

2.6. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF A PART-TIME JOB

Nowadays, students are being involved in part-time employment rapidly. The reason is students want to get experience or support their families in terms of finance. This trend is in every part of the world, for example, the USA, the UK, Australia, and many other countries. All countries haven't concluded whether part-time jobs are beneficial; this is questionable (Shinhiro & Kentaro, 2018). ShareThis is the general conclusion

Part-time employment is advantageous for students, and there are also some opinions that part-time employment negatively affects students' performance (Osborne et al., 2004). The effects of a part-time job may depend on the individual's personal characteristics. Some students have good time management and dealing skills to cope with work and education simultaneously. Some students have a good sense of responsibility and deal with both sides.

Part-time jobs improve and enhance the non-cognitive skills of the students that educational institutions cannot assess. Part-time jobs provide students with experience, enabling them to be independent and successful individuals & employees in the future. On the contrary, part-time jobs can also negatively affect students' academic performance. Because when students do part-time jobs, they cannot find enough time for their homework. They feel sleepy and tired at home and in the classroom. Their routine gets disturbed. In this way, they cannot properly focus on their students and can't learn much compared to their class, resulting in low grades and poor performance.

Further, this behavior can lead to institutional dropout (Rokicka, 2014). Students are very aware of the importance of education. They could find ways to deal with the workplace and educational activities simultaneously. The primary thing is that students must choose part-time jobs according to their discipline and field so that they can easily understand the workplace, and that can be helpful for them in their future careers.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY RESEARCH DESIGN

This research utilized a qualitative approach, which asks broad questions and collects participant data. A structured interview was used as a data collection technique to examine the effect of employment on students' academic achievement and satisfaction. Part-time job was viewed as the independent variable, and students' academic achievement was viewed as the dependent variable.

3.1. POPULATION AND SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

All students engaged with part-time jobs at International Islamic University were the population of the research study. The sample of 14 respondents (7 students of B. Ed from a Distance Education program and 7 students of B. Ed from a regular program from the department of education) was selected through purposive sampling technique because the researcher recruited those students who have part-time jobs.

3.2. INSTRUMENTATION

A structured interview was used to collect data. The structured interview consisted of open-ended questions. The interview questions were based on the positive and negative effects of part-time jobs, factors that affect part-time jobs and the number of hours spent on part-time jobs. The structured interviews were done in consultation with the experts. Data analysis was done by thematic analysis. Themes were generated from the responses of the respondents.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1. EFFECTS OF PART-TIME JOBS ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

After analyzing the data from the respondents on the effects of part-time jobs on students' academic achievement, the researcher found;

4.1.1. POSITIVE EFFECTS OF PART-TIME JOB REGULAR STUDENTS

Some respondents provide feedback that part-time jobs motivate them to do their studies properly. All respondents responded that part-time jobs provide them with professional life experience. Most students replied that a part-time job makes them confident and independent.

Some respondents responded that a part-time job enables them to be aware of discoveries related to education.

4.1.2. DISTANCE EDUCATION PROGRAM STUDENTS

All of the respondents provided feedback that part-time job provides them with experience related to professional life. Most students respond that a part-time job makes them more responsible and aware of their studies. Most students respond that a part-time job enables them to manage their time.

4.1.3. ADVERSE EFFECTS OF PART-TIME JOB REGULAR STUDENTS

All of the students responded that part-time job makes them tired and sleepy. The majority of the students provide feedback that they cannot correctly manage their time for studies due to part-time jobs, which provides them with stress.

4.1.4. DISTANCE LEARNING PROGRAM STUDENTS

All the Students provide feedback that a part-time job does not harm their academic achievement and satisfaction.

4.1.5. FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE STUDENTS TO DO PART-TIME JOB

After analyzing the data from the respondents, the researcher found the following factors that influence students to do part-time jobs:

4.1.6. REGULAR STUDENTS

Most respondents provide feedback that they do part-time jobs to get experience and knowledge about professional life. Some respondents responded that they are doing the job due to their interest. Some students responded that they do part-time jobs to fulfill their personal and basic needs.

4.2. DISTANCE LEARNING PROGRAM STUDENTS

All respondents provided feedback that they do part-time jobs to get experience and knowledge about professional life. Some students respond that they do part-time jobs due to financial problems.

4.2.1. HOURS SPENT ON PART TIME JOB AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

After analyzing the data from the respondent's researcher found:

4.2.2. REGULAR STUDENTS

Most students responded that they spent 7 hours on part-time jobs and had a CGPA of 3.5. Some respondents responded that they spent 6 hours working part-time, and their CGPA was 3.8. Some respondents responded that they spent 8 hours on work, and their CGP was 3.3.

4.2.3. DISTANCE LEARNING PROGRAM STUDENTS

Almost all respondents responded that they worked 6 hours on their job, and their GPA was 3.8.

5. RESULTS

Research shows that most of the regular students respond that a part-time job provides them with experience in professional life and makes them independent.

Research reveals that part-time jobs provide most distance learning students with time management skills and experience.

Research depicts that most regular students face stress, shortage of time and fatigue.

Research shows that all distance learning program students do not face any problems due to part-time jobs.

Research indicates that most regular and distance learning program students do part-time jobs to gain experience and knowledge about their professional lives.

Research shows that most regular students work part-time for 7 hours, and their CGPA is 3.5.

Research shows that most distance learning program students work part-time for 6 hours, and their CGPA was 3.8.

5.1. DISCUSSIONS

Part-time jobs have been practiced by students at different levels for most years. Part-time employment is a type of job that consists of fewer hours than a full-time job. Students' academic achievement and their satisfaction related to their studies are influenced by part-time employment. A part-time job is a help for individuals who may not get a full-time job for some reason. Part-time jobs enable individuals to fulfill their needs for whom the salary package is too low to compensate for their basic needs. The study's primary objective was to examine the effects of part-time jobs on students' academic achievement and satisfaction at the university level. The study found that part-time jobs affect them both positively and negatively. Students provide feedback that enhancement in motivation, experience, confidence and independence are the positive effects of the part-time jobs. Regular students respond that part-time jobs make them tired and they cannot manage their study time.

However, distance learning program students did not face any adverse effects. Further study found that working students argue that they do part-time jobs to get experience and earn money to fulfill their personal needs and for their interests. Moreover, a study shows that when students will have more working hours, it will decrease their CGPA. The results of the present study are in line with the findings of studies conducted by Kwadzo (2014), Rokicka (2014), Carney et al. (2005), Sekiguchi (2012), Patton et al. (2009) and Tessema et al. (2014). The results of these studies are discussed one by one in the following paragraphs. Carney et al. (2005) conducted a study on the impact of part-time jobs on students' health and academic performance at the University of Glasgow, UK. Quantitative research methods were used by the researcher, comprising 756 respondents. The study results show that these students were always missing regular classes, which hampered their studies.

Patton et al. (2009) studied students doing part-time jobs and their part-time workplace problems in Australia. The researcher used a qualitative research method comprising 76 respondents. The results of the study show that the majority of the students were facing problems and challenges. Sekiguchi (2012) carried out a study on part-time working students and their career development in Japan. The study was quantitative and comprised of 123 respondents. Results of the study show that a part-time job is helpful for the development of their career as part-time work provides experience to students. Kwadzo (2014) studied International students who were engaged in part-time jobs. The research was quantitative and comprised of 20 respondents. The study's findings reveal that part-time jobs give them experience, financial aid, a healthy lifestyle and good communication skills.

Rokicka (2014) conducted a study on the impact of students' part-time work on educational outcomes in England. The study was quantitative, and the sample was 150 students engaged in part-time jobs. The study results show that part-time gives them different skills that cannot be taught in real classroom situations. Tessema et al. (2014) studied the effects of part-time jobs on student satisfaction and academic performance in the USA. Quantitative research methods were applied. The sample comprised 5223 respondents. The study results show that part-time jobs positively and negatively impact students' academic achievement and performance, but students should not work more than 10 hours.

6. CONCLUSION

- Based on the study findings, it can be concluded that part-time jobs positively and negatively affect them. Students provide feedback that enhancement in motivation, experience, confidence and independence are the positive effects of the part-time jobs. Regular students respond that part-time jobs make them tired and they cannot manage their study time. However, distance learning program students did not face any adverse effects.

- Working students argue they do part-time jobs to get experience and earn money to fulfill their needs and interests.
- The CGPA of the regular students who work part-time for 7 hours was 3.5. Those who worked 6 hours had a CGPA of 3.8, and students who worked for 8 hours was
- Distance learning Program students work for 6 hours, and their CGPA was 3.8. It shows that when students will have more working hours, it will decrease their CGPA.

6.1. RECOMMENDATIONS

- In light of the present study, the following recommendations were made:
- Part-time students might take their capacities to do the jobs during their studies. Students might be aware of their potential to cope with the conflict of studies and work.
- Due to economic pressure, the government might provide scholarships to students so that they don't do part-time jobs to fulfill their basic needs.
- Teachers might understand the engagement of working students, so the stress of these students may be reduced to some extent and might guide the students on how they can manage their time.
- Part-time students might improve working conditions. Students may work part-time with moderate working hours to perform well at the university.

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